

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The influence of leadership style, teamwork and organizational learning on performance through job satisfaction of state vocational school teachers

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to identify and analyze this study to determine and analyze the influence of leadership style on teacher job satisfaction. Teamwork on teacher job satisfaction. Organizational learning affects teacher job satisfaction. Leadership style affects teacher performance. Teamwork affects teacher performance. Organizational learning affects teacher performance. Job satisfaction affects performance. Leadership style affects performance through job satisfaction. Teamwork affects performance through teacher job satisfaction. Organizational learning affects performance through teacher job satisfaction. The population in this study amounted to 62 teachers and data analysis using SmartPLS. The conclusion of this study is that leadership style has a positive and significant effect on teacher job satisfaction. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on teacher job satisfaction. Organizational learning has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. This means that the better the leadership style, the better the performance. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. Organizational learning has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on performance through teacher job satisfaction. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on performance through teacher job satisfaction. Learning has a positive and significant impact on organizational performance through job satisfaction.

Keywords: Leadership Style; Teamwork; Organizational Learning; Job Satisfaction; Performance

1. Introduction

Education is a conscious effort so that humans develop their potential through the learning process. Schools have components that are interrelated with each other and work together to achieve common goals. In this case, each component or human education provider in schools needs to have good abilities to achieve the school's goals as an educational institution (1).

The perpetrators of activities in school organizations are principals, teachers, and employees. The teacher is the main actor in achieving the achievement of learning objectives in schools. In achieving the achievement of school goals, teachers are the main component in making schools achieve their goals. The success of schools in achieving their goals is also strongly influenced by the performance of teachers in carrying out their duties so teacher performance is an important demand for achieving educational success. The achievement of school goals, both in quantity and quality, is largely determined by the teacher's performance.

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Teacher performance is an important element in education, but it is also a determinant of the high and low quality of education. Teacher performance is carried out by the teacher in carrying out the duties of a teacher as an educator. The quality of teacher performance is very decisive in the quality of educational outcomes because the teacher is the figure who most often interacts directly with students during the learning process (2).

Teacher performance is the main ability that is observed during the learning process. One of the indicators of a teacher being successful and performing in carrying out his professional duties is being able to make good learning programs which include learning planning, implementation, or learning processes, as well as assessing and following up on learning outcomes. One of the factors that improve teacher performance is leadership style (3). The relationship between teachers and organizations in schools cannot be separated from their leadership. A wise and good organizational leader should always try to pay attention to their passion and enthusiasm for work. Of course, the leadership must have the ability to manage and then direct, influence, command, and motivate employees to obtain the desired goals of the organization

Another factor that can improve performance is the teamwork of (4). Teamwork is a group of people who work together to achieve the same goal and that goal will be more easily obtained by dividing tasks is a work scheduling in an organization while a team is a work group consisting of several people with equal competence, where they work dependently in carrying out work in one organization.

Table 1 Research Gap Past Research

Effect Between Variables	Researcher	Research result
Leadership style on job satisfaction	(11), (12), (13) and (14)	Significant
	(15)	Not significant
Teamwork on job satisfaction	(16) (17), (18) and (19)	Significant
	(20)	Not significant
Organizational learning on job satisfaction	(21), (6), (22), (23)	Significant
	(24)	Not significant
Leadership style on performance	(25), (26) and (27)	Significant
	(28)	Not significant
Teamwork on performance	(29) and (4)	Significant
	(30)	Not significant
Organizational learning on performance	(31) and (5)	Significant
	(32)	Not significant
Job satisfaction on performance	(33), (34) and (35)	Significant
	(36)	Not significant
Leadership style on performance through job satisfaction	(37) and (38)	Significant
		Not significant
Teamwork on performance through job satisfaction	(26)	Significant
		Not significant
Organizational learning on performance through satisfaction	(6)	Significant
		Not significant

Source: Results of Previous Research Reviews , (2022)

Another factor that can improve performance is organizational learning (5). Organizational learning greatly influences the development of an organization. According to (6), organizational learning illustrates that learning is a prerequisite for the success of a change and organizational performance. According to (7), organizational learning is where the

individuals in it continuously increase their capacity to produce something they want. Organizations where new and broad mindsets are learned (8) argues that job satisfaction is a person's perspective, both positive and negative about his work. Everyone who works expects to get satisfaction from his place of work. Job satisfaction is an individual thing because each individual will have a different level of satisfaction according to the values that apply to each individual. The more aspects of work that are by individual desires, the higher the level of perceived satisfaction (9).

Job satisfaction is a positive attitude towards work in a person. Usually, people will feel satisfied with the work that has been or is being carried out, if what is done is considered to have met expectations, following the purpose of working. Job satisfaction shows a match between one's expectations that arise and the rewards provided by the job, so job satisfaction is also closely related to the theory of justice, psychological agreement, and motivation, (10)

Based on the results of the study of previous studies, the authors found that there were gaps in the results of research regarding the factors that affect performance such as leadership style variables, teamwork, organizational learning, and job satisfaction.

Based on the problems that exist in the research location, inconsistencies in previous research, and suggestions from previous research, the researchers are interested in conducting a study entitled "The Influence of Leadership Style, Teamwork and Organizational Learning on Performance Through Job Satisfaction of State Vocational High School Teachers, South Konawe Regency".

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1. Leadership Style

By (39) explains that leadership style is a set of strategies used by a leader to influence employees so that organizational goals are achieved or it can also be said that leadership style is a pattern of strategies or behavior patterns that are preferred and often applied by a leader. Then Hasibuan (2013), leadership style is a way used by a leader to be able to influence employees, to want to work together and work productively to achieve organizational goals. (40), leadership style is a complex process carried out by a leader which aims to influence others to achieve a mission, task or goal and direct the organization in a more reasonable way. Measurement of leadership style refers to the opinion (41) namely to transformational leadership, transactional leadership and *laissez-faire leadership*.

2.2. Team Work

By (42) state that teamwork is a group whose individual efforts produce higher performance than the sum of individual inputs. Work team generate positive synergies through coordinated efforts. This means that the performance achieved by a team is better than the performance per individual in an organization or a company. This statement is also supported by (43), which states that the effectiveness of an effective team or team is a work team whose members collaborate with each other to achieve common goals and have a mutually supportive attitude in teamwork. Indicators of teamwork from (44) are providing advice, cooperation, communication, team spirit, adaptability, coordination and acceptance of suggestions.

2.3. Organizational Learning

According to (45) " Organizational learning is the idea an organization could learn and knowledge could be stored over time. Organizational learning is an organization that continuously learns to increase its capacity to change (46). According to (6) organizational learning illustrates that learning is a prerequisite for the success of a change and organizational performance. According to (7), organizational learning is where the individuals in it continuously increase their capacity to produce something desired. Organizations where new and broad mindsets are learned. Organizations where group aspirations are liberated. And organizations where individuals in them learn how to learn together. According to (7) organizational learning indicators are system thinking, mental models, personal mastery and team learning.

2.4. Job Satisfaction

By (8) argues that job satisfaction is a person's perspective, both positive and negative about his work. The more aspects of work that are in accordance with individual desires, the higher the level of perceived satisfaction (9). By (47) argues that job satisfaction is a person's perspective, both positive and negative about his work. While (48) revealed that job satisfaction is a positive attitude and involves a healthy adjustment of employees to work conditions and situations, including financial problems, social conditions, physical conditions and psychological conditions.

Job satisfaction is a positive attitude towards work in a person. Usually people will feel satisfied with the work that has been or is being carried out, if what is done is considered to have met expectations, in accordance with the purpose of working. Job satisfaction shows a match between one's expectations that arise and the rewards provided by the job, so job satisfaction is also closely related to the theory of justice, psychological agreement and motivation, (10). Job satisfaction indicators according to (49) are the nature of work, supervision, current pay and relationships with coworkers.

2.5. Performance

Performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him (50). Performance is the periodic determination of the operational effectiveness of the organization, its part of the organization and its employees based on predetermined targets, standards and criteria, (51) . According to (52), performance is the result of work in quality and quantity that can be achieved by an employee in carrying out tasks in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Permendikbud No. 15 of 2018 explains that performance indicators are planning lessons, implementing learning, assessing learning outcomes and carrying out follow-up on assessment results.

From the literature review. The conceptual framework of this study is shown below:

Figure 1 Research Conceptual Framework

The hypotheses that can be formulated in this study are as follows:

- Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency
- Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency
- Organizational learning has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency
- Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on the performance of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency
- Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on the performance of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency
- Organizational learning has a positive and significant effect on the performance of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency
- Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the performance of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency
- Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency
- Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction of State Vocational High School Teachers, South Konawe Regency
- Learning has a positive and significant impact on organizational performance through job satisfaction of State Vocational High School Teachers, Konawe Selatan Regency

3. Methods

This study aims to examine and examine the causal relationship between the influence of leadership style , teamwork and organizational learning on performance through job satisfaction of teachers at the Konawe Selatan District Vocational High School. The population in this study were all PNS teachers of the Konawe Selatan Regency State Vocational High School, which amounted to 62 people and all of them were used as samples. Measurement of data in this study using a Likert scale . In data processing, the Likert scale is included in the interval scale, the determination of the Likert scale of this study is made on a scale of 1 to 5. The guideline for measuring all variables is to use 5 points, where if there is an answer with a low weight then a score of 1 is given and so on so that the answer with a high weight is given a score of 5. This research data was tested using SmartPLS 3.0 software.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Evaluation of the Measurement Model (*Outer Moder*)

outer model measurement model with reflective indicators can be done through testing the validity of each indicator on each construct and testing the reliability of the construct.

4.1.1 Evaluating Convergent Validity

Table 1 Convergent Validity Test Results

Research variable	Variable Indicator	<i>Outer loading</i>	Meaning
Leadership style	To transformational leadership	0.812	Valid
	Transactional leadership	0.857	Valid
	Laissez-faire leadership	0.912	Valid
Teamwork	Giving advice	0.904	Valid
	Cooperation	0.832	Valid
	Communication	0.809	Valid
	Team spirit	0.841	Valid
	Adaptability	0.826	Valid
	Coordination	0.777	Valid
	Advice acceptance	0.720	Valid
Organizational Learning	Systems Thinking	0.899	Valid
	Mental Model	0.869	Valid
	Personal Mastery	0.894	Valid
	Study Team	0.736	Valid
	Building a Shared Vision	0.726	Valid
Job satisfaction	Nature of work	0.884	Valid
	Supervision	0.902	Valid
	Pay now	0.868	Valid
	Relationship with coworkers	0.881	Valid
Teacher Performance	Planning lessons	0.861	Valid
	Carry out learning	0.910	Valid
	Assessing learning outcomes	0.892	Valid
	Carry out follow-up on the results of the assessment	0.879	Valid

Source: Data Processed 2022

Based on the table, it is known that the loading value of all the variables tested is known, where it is known that there is no *outer loading value* below the predetermined limit of 0.7. Starting from the variables of leadership style , teamwork , organizational learning, job satisfaction and teacher performance, it can be said that all indicators used in this study are valid .

4.1.2 Discriminant Validity

The next evaluation is by comparing the AVE root value with the correlation between constructs. The recommended result is that the AVE root value should be higher than the correlation between constructs. The model has better discriminant validity if the square root of the AVE for each construct is greater than the correlation between the constructs in the model.

Table 2 Latent Variable Correlation

Variable	Leadership style	Job satisfaction	Teamwork	Teacher Performance	Organizational Learning
Leadership style	0.861				
Job satisfaction	0.591	0.884			
Teamwork	0.343	0.765	0.817		
Teacher Performance	0.761	0.850	0.683	0.886	
Organizational Learning	0.439	0.710	0.683	0.713	0.828

Source: Data Processed 2022

Based on the table, it can be seen that the AVE root value for each variable is greater than the correlation value so that the construct in this research model can still be said to have good *discriminant validity* . On the basis of this, it is concluded that all indicators and variables are valid and meet the requirements of *discriminant validity* .

4.2. Research Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is carried out to answer the problems posed in this study with the results of data analysis carried out. Hypothesis testing was carried out according to the research framework carried out to analyze and test directly and indirectly between exogenous and endogenous variables with a mediation model.

Source: Data Processed 2022

Figure 2 Results of Data Analysis Using SmartPLS

4.2.1 Direct Effect Test

Hypothesis testing is done by looking at *the output path coefficient from the bootstrap* resampling results as follows:

Table 3 Results of Direct Hypothesis Testing

Influence Between Variables	Original Sample	P Values	Note:
Leadership style → Job Satisfaction	0.315	0.000	Received
Teamwork → Job Satisfaction	0.490	0.000	Received
Organizational Learning → Job Satisfaction	0.247	0.009	Received
Leadership Style → Teacher Performance	0.417	0.000	Received
Teamwork → Teacher Performance	0.140	0.038	Received
Organizational Learning → Teacher Performance	0.162	0.021	Received
Job Satisfaction → Teacher Performance	0.380	0.001	Received

Source: Data Processed 2022

4.2.2 Indirect Effect Test

The test of leadership style on teacher performance through job satisfaction. The results of the analysis of this research can be explained as follows:

Table 4 Indirect Hypothesis Testing Results

Influence Between Variables	P Values	Ke t
Leadership Style → Job satisfaction → Teacher Performance	0.007	Received
Teamwork → Job satisfaction → Teacher Performance	0.020	Received
Organizational Learning → Job satisfaction → Teacher Performance	0.025	Received

Source: Data Processed 2022

4.3. The Effect of Leadership Style on Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that the leadership style variable has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of teachers at the State Vocational High School in South Konawe Regency . This shows that a high leadership style will significantly affect the achievement of teacher job satisfaction. This means that if the leadership style can be used as a factor that can increase teacher job satisfaction. The high leadership style will greatly affect the increase in teacher job satisfaction.

The results of this study are similar to the findings of (11), (12), (13) and (14) found that leadership style on job satisfaction had a significant effect on job satisfaction. These findings show that leadership can increase one's job satisfaction

4.4. The Effect of Teamwork on Job Satisfaction

Teamwork variable has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of teachers at the State Vocational High School in South Konawe Regency . This shows that high teamwork will significantly affect the achievement of teacher job satisfaction. This means that if teamwork can be used as a factor that can increase teacher job satisfaction. High teamwork will greatly affect the increase in teacher job satisfaction.

The results of this study are the same as the findings of (16), (53), (18) found that teamwork has a significant effect on job satisfaction, so it can be understood that teamwork can increase one's job satisfaction when working in an organization.

4.5. The Effect of Organizational Learning on Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that the organizational learning variable has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of teachers at the Konawe Selatan District Vocational High School . This shows that high organizational learning will significantly affect the achievement of teacher job satisfaction. This means that organizational learning can be used as a factor that can increase teacher job satisfaction. The high level of organizational learning will greatly affect the increase in teacher job satisfaction

The results of this study are similar to the findings of (21), (6), (22) found that organizational learning has a significant effect on job satisfaction. This means that the better the organizational learning process is carried out, it will increase job satisfaction.

4.6. Influence of Leadership Style on Performance

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that the leadership style variable has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the teachers of the State Vocational High School in South Konawe Regency . This shows that a high leadership style will significantly affect the achievement of teacher performance. This means that if the leadership style can be used as a factor that can improve teacher performance.

The results of this study are the same as the findings of (25) and (27) found that leadership style has a significant effect on performance, meaning that it can be understood that leadership style can contribute to the improvement of one's performance.

4.7. The Effect of Teamwork on Performance

teamwork variable has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the teachers of the Konawe Selatan District Vocational High School . This shows that high teamwork will significantly affect the achievement of teacher performance. This means that if teamwork can be used as a factor that can improve teacher performance. High teamwork will greatly affect the improvement of teacher performance.

The results of this study are similar to the findings of (54) and (4) found that teamwork has a significant effect on performance, meaning that the better the cooperation between individuals, the more work they have, of course this will very good for the organization.

4.8. The Effect of Organizational Learning on Performance

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that organizational learning variables have a positive and significant effect on performance, this shows that good and bad organizational learning will be able to improve teacher performance.

The results of this study are the same as the findings of (31) and (55) found that organizational learning has a significant effect on performance, this shows that organizational learning can improve one's performance, this is certainly good for existing human resources and development. organization.

4.9. The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Performance

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that the job satisfaction variable has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the teachers of the State Vocational High School in South Konawe Regency . This shows that high job satisfaction will significantly affect the achievement of teacher performance. This means that if job satisfaction can be used as a factor that can improve teacher performance. High job satisfaction will greatly affect the improvement of teacher performance. The results of this study are the same as the findings of (33), (34) and (35) found that job satisfaction has a significant effect on performance, this shows that the better one's job satisfaction will also increase performance. them in the organization.

4.10. The Influence of Leadership Style on Performance Through Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that leadership style has a significant influence on performance through job satisfaction at the Konawe Selatan District Vocational High School. Job satisfaction variable is able to mediate pen on teacher performance. This shows that high job satisfaction will significantly affect the achievement of teacher performance. This means that if job satisfaction can be used as a factor that can improve teacher performance. High job satisfaction will greatly affect the improvement of teacher performance. The results of this study are similar to the

findings of (38) who found that job satisfaction can mediate leadership style on performance. This means that job satisfaction is an intervening variable between leadership style and employee performance because the value of the indirect influence is greater than the direct influence

4.11. The Effect of Teamwork on Performance through Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that teamwork has a significant effect on performance through job satisfaction at the Konawe Selatan Regency State Vocational High School.

According to (4) one of the dominant factors to improve performance is a good work team . Cooperation is a group of people who work together to achieve the same goal and that goal will be more easily obtained by dividing tasks is a work scheduling in an organization. The results of this study are the same as the findings of (26) in their research, which found that job satisfaction was able to mediate the effect of teamwork on performance, meaning that job satisfaction was able to be a solution to the inconsistency of the findings of teamwork on performance.

4.12. The Effect of Organizational Learning on Performance Through Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that organizational learning has a significant effect on performance through job satisfaction at the Konawe Selatan District Vocational High School. Organizational learning applied to the organization is expected to bring about better changes for the progress of the organization by always supporting the learning carried out by human resources. (55) say that one of the factors that can improve performance is organizational learning. High employee job satisfaction is needed for every employee because with job satisfaction behavior employees can work in accordance with the values and goals of the organization.

The results of this study are similar to the findings of (6) who found that job satisfaction can mediate the effect of organizational learning on performance. The meaning is that satisfaction can overcome the inconsistency of the effect of organizational learning on performance.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion, several conclusions can be drawn from this study, namely leadership style has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency. This means that the better the style , the better the job satisfaction. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency. This means that the better the teamwork , the higher job satisfaction . Organizational learning has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency. This means that the better organizational learning will increase job satisfaction . Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency. This means that the better the leadership style , it will increase the performance . Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on the performance of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency. This means that the better the teamwork , the better the performance . Organizational learning has a positive and significant effect on the performance of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency. This means that the better the organizational learning, the better the performance . Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the performance of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency. This means that the better job satisfaction it will improve performance . Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency. This means that job satisfaction is able to mediate leadership style on teacher performance, and it is also known that the nature of mediation in this influence is partial mediation. Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency. This means that job satisfaction is able to mediate teamwork on teacher performance, and it is also known that the nature of mediation in this influence is partial mediation. Learning has a positive and significant impact on organizational performance through job satisfaction of State Vocational High School Teachers in South Konawe Regency. This means that job satisfaction is able to mediate organizational learning on teacher performance. and it is also known that the nature of mediation in this influence is partial mediation. For further research, replace or add factors that can affect performance such as motivation and career development.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest

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